

CONCEPT AND ITS TYPES IN LITERARY TEXT

Sobirova Nigina Aliyevna

University of Tashkent for Applied Sciences "Department of languages" English teacher

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7558363>

Abstract. *In this article are given the notion of concept and the usage concept in the literary texts.*

Keywords: *concept, time, notion, continuity, duration, experience, analysis, cognitive linguistics, cognitive psychology, cultural linguistics.*

The thought is expressed at a relatively complete level and it seems necessary for the speaker to add something to it that was not thought of beforehand, an expression is an auxiliary construction. It means concepts. Concept expands, completes, realizes and clarifies the content of the main expression of the previous sentence. This is a very natural case for oral speech. It is an idea that is left behind in the main sentence during the conversation and it is considered extremely necessary to say can be filled through constructions. At present the term "concept" is widely used in different fields of linguistics. The study of concept has a great importance as it is connected with cognitive linguistics, cognitive psychology, cultural linguistics and with cognition and transferring information.

Many researchers formulated the characteristics of the "concept" in their works. For example, D.S. Likhachov used this term to refer to the generalized cognitive unit, which reflects the phenomena of reality, depending on education, personal experience, professional and social experience of a native speaker

Yu.S. Stepanov believes that a concept is the "content of the notion", A.P. Babushkin regards the concept as a mental unit which reflects the object of real or imaginative world and is kept in the national memory of native speakers. In the Brief Dictionary of Cognitive Terms the concept is defined as "operational meaningful unit of memory, mental lexicon, conceptual system, brain language, and the whole picture of the world reflected in the human mind"

The concept can be a part of the world picture as well. It reflects the values of both the individual person and the entire linguistic community. The concept is valuable for a particular culture, which is expressed by a large number of linguistic units, which can be embodied in proverbs and sayings, poetry and prose. They are a kind of symbols or emblems, specifically pointing to the text, situation or knowledge that created them.

It is important to say that despite the variety of interpretations of concept, linguistic researchers have agreed that concept is a mental representation, "a unit of mental activity". In general usage the term mainly denotes "idea" or "notion". In a narrower sense it is a mental symbol sometimes defined as a "unit of knowledge", built from other units which act as the concept's characteristics. The concept has a cognitive status and does not exist outside mind. In linguistic science the notion of linguistic personality appeared long ago: the information about the possibility of reconstructing personality through language, the view of the world, consciousness was noted in the works of A.A. Potebnaya, L.V. Scherba, G. O. Vinokur, B. A. Larin and other scholars at the beginning of the XX century. The structure of the linguistic personality is described in most detail in the works of Yu.N. Karaulov on the material of the Russian language. Many provisions of this work concerning the structure of linguistic personality served for the quality of

initial theoretical prerequisites of our work. Nevertheless, the problem of linguistic personality in English appears to be elaborated insufficiently. It is possible only to point out few researches on English material devoted to the problems of linguistic personality: linguistic personality in individual style of Hemingway; the concept of linguistic personality in English in comparison to Russian (on the example of the analysis of various translations of the play B. Shaw "Pygmalion; general and distinctive structure of linguistic personality in Russian and English variants of professional sports language). A certain attention in some articles is paid to particular aspects of LP. In foreign linguistics, the problem of linguistic personality is generally dealt within psycholinguistic aspect.

The most important of the linguistic features of the literary text is that it contains emotional words, dialect words, slang and argons, figurative words, similar in meaning, similar in form, similar in pronunciation and related meaningful words, as well as units such as idiom, proverb and matal, application and aphorism are given a wide place.

The method of concept research is not identical in case of literature and folklore. Analysis of the concept LIFE based on the phraseology is given by V. Maslova

1) outlining of the concept core based on dictionary definitions of the same entry during different historical periods;

2) establishing the periphery of concept using associative experiment;

3) ideographic processing of the concept structure (semantic analysis);

4) determining the concept place in general conceptual scheme – the first level of conceptualization;

5) selection of background information (from dictionaries of different types: etymological, explanatory, mythological, cultural, ethno-linguistic, etc.) for each semantic field, group, subgroup;

6) singling out the common and differential, general-cultural and ethno-cultural components from background information within all semantic fields;

7) outlining the associative-figurative complex of components pointed out on the second level – the second level of conceptualization V. Maslova

V. Maslova considers the concept as a part of the national conceptual domain (linguoculturological approach). This type of conceptual analysis involves the study of semantic structure and pragmatics of a certain word that is interpreted as a cultural phenomenon with its own etymology. For establishing the semantic volume of the concept, the scholar offers:

1) to define the reference situation including a concept, and in case of a literary text this operation is carried out on its basis;

2) to establish the place of a concept in the language picture of the world and linguistic consciousness of the nation through appellation to the linguistic and encyclopedic dictionaries, besides we consider the dictionary definition as a concept core;

3) to appeal to etymology and its features;

4) since dictionary interpretations give only a general idea of the word meaning, as well as encyclopedic dictionaries – of the concept, it is necessary to involve to the analysis a variety of contexts: poetic, scientific, philosophical, journalistic, proverbs and sayings, etc.;

5) received results should be compared with the analysis of associative links of keyword unit (concept core), for example, analyzing the concept of “time” enables to establish its close relationship with the concept of “future”;

6) if the important culture concept was selected for analysis, it must be frequently repeated and interpreted in painting, music, sculpture, etc.

Thus, the analysis of linguistic literature has shown that the problem of linguistic personality, especially the one on English material, is studied insufficiently. Any other work based on complex research of LP similar to our research material chosen by us for revealing LP in literary discourse is absent.

The concept and the meaning of the word have some similarities. Human mind reflects the objective and subjective reality. Both the concept and the meaning are the reflection of reality (objective and subjective). They have cognitive nature and present the result of the reflection and cognition of reality by the human mind.

On the other hand, they have certain differences. The meaning and concept are the products of the different levels. Concepts are regarded as mental units, and meanings refer to linguistic entity. Concept is a product of cognitive human consciousness, while meaning is the product of linguistic consciousness. Meaning in relation to concept appears as a part of its content, which is relevant to linguocultural community. Many cognitive linguists agree that components of lexical meaning reflect only significant conceptual features, but not all of them. The structure of concept is much more complicated and more varied than the lexical meaning of the words.

Nowadays there are two approaches to the notion of concept in modern linguistics. They are *cognitive*, and from the point of view of cultural study—*linguo-cultural*. Each approach, according to certain features, highlights the specific properties of concept.

Researchers of the first approach consider concept as a cognitive linguistic phenomenon. From the positions of cognitive linguistics “concept” is considered to be a complex mental unit, means of representation of knowledge structures. Concept is the information which an individual knows, thinks, suggests, and imagines about the objects of the world. According to the cognitive approach concept is connected with verbal means of expression. Though concepts exist in the individual’s mind, they are verbalized in language with the help of linguistic means. Concept is expressed by words, phrases and by sentences, idioms, collocations and even by the entire text.

Concept has a certain structure that is not rigid; it is a necessary condition for the existence of the concept and its entry into the conceptual realm. Concept includes all the mental characteristics of a phenomenon and provides the understanding of reality.

Other researchers such as V.I. Karasik, G.Slyshkin, S.G. Vorkochev, Z.D. Popova, V.A. Maslova, I.A. Sternin and others assert that there are three components composing “concept”: **notional; imagery and evaluative.**

The notional layer is based on factual information, i.e. the basic, essential and distinctive features of the concept. Imagery layer is based upon the principle of analogy, and evaluative component is connected with axiological and cultural significance.

Summing up the results of the research done in this sphere we can say that concepts mean as components of human cognition in the cognitive science disciplines of linguistics, psychology, and philosophy, where are regularly formalized in mathematics, computer science, databases and artificial intelligence. In informal use the word *concept* often just means any idea. Concepts exist in people’s mind, they can be verbalized in language. In language concept can be presented by separate words, phrases, sentences or the whole text. The choice of verbal shape depends on the personal meaning, mental representation and the internal lexicon of the speaker, which are all interconnected with each other.

REFERENCES

1. Likhachev, D.S. Concept of the Russian language Text. /D.S. Likhachev//Proceedings of the Academy of Sciences of the USSR. 1993.
2. Arnold. I.V. Fundamentals of scientific research in linguistics/ I.V.Arnold.-M.: Higher school, 1991.
3. Arnold I.V. Stylistics of modern English. M.: Enlightenment, 1990
4. Maslova, V.A. Linguoculturology Text. / V.A. Maslova.-M.: Ed. Center “Academy”, 2001
5. Popova Z.D., Sternin I.A. On the problem of unification of linguocognitive terminology.// Introduction to cognitive linguistics. Kemerovo, 2004
6. Ashurova D. U. Derived word in the light of communication theory language.-Tashkent: Fan, 1991.